

Editorial

Dear Readers,

It would be tempting to start this editorial by bringing attention once again to the effects of the pandemics. The impact of Covid19 on scholarly life is nowadays the leitmotif of most academic publications. In fact, in the last issue, I also made a point of saying that our life would gradually be getting back on track. In retrospect, this was a snap judgement. Looking around us, we can see that the situation is still too uncertain to make any kind of predictions. At ESPES, we have full respect for those who are devotedly trying to make sense of the present time. Yet, as an editorial team, we choose to commit to the future.

In this spirit, as many of you might have noticed, we have recently released a number of calls for papers for upcoming issues of the journal. While we consider Thematic Symposia an especially useful format to address a topic in its complexity and diversity, in the future we aim to focus more on the publication of Special Issues. The support of a variety of committed guest scholars will thus continue to be crucial and I trust the journal will benefit again from such support, as it luckily has so far. To further satisfy our readers, we also have a plan to renew the journal website and make it more user-friendly and easily accessible.

Recently, our efforts as editors have been rewarded by the journal's acceptance in the lists of recognised scientific journals in both Italy and Finland. These acknowledgements encourage us to look even further ahead. In this regard, we are striving to do our best to ensure that the journal may soon be approved for inclusion into the Scopus and Web of Science indexation services.

These days, however, have also brought some very sad news to the editorial team of this journal. We were struck by the unexpected passing of Jana Sošková, the founder of ESPES and long-time Editor-in-chief. Only six months ago we celebrated her seventieth birthday with the publication of an interview and a translation of one of her most fascinating studies. Today, Prof. Sošková is unfortunately no longer with us. We will always remember her involvement in and contribution to a wide range of topics in contemporary aesthetics, both theoretical and historical, as well as her many presentations and public discussions. She was an important member of the Institute that was and is behind this journal and was involved in many of the often complicated decisions the editors had to deal with in the past. Now she is gone, but her memory lives on in each new issue we publish.

On a brighter note, let me now introduce you to the present issue of ESPES: *Everyday Aesthetics: European Perspectives*. The idea of dedicating a thematic issue to *Everyday Aesthetics* originated during the congress of the International Association for Aesthetics that was held in Belgrade, Serbia, in the summer of 2019. The collaboration with Guest Editors Elisabetta

Di Stefano and Sanna Lehtinen resulted in the idea of focusing on contemporary interpretations of Everyday Aesthetics that identify its different roots in the history of continental aesthetics. I am grateful to both of them for the numerous discussions we had and for their dedication and attention in evaluating the submissions. I am very pleased with the outcome of this cooperation. Surely the time invested in preparing this issue was well spent and I am confident that the variety of topics included therein will be of interest to the readers of this journal.

I want to conclude by thanking those who have assisted me in the publication of Vol.10 of *ESPES*. I acknowledge and thank Jana Migašová and Tomáš Timko for their graphic help in designing captivating covers for this year's issues of the journal. I am especially grateful to the members of the Editorial Board for their various support. Finally, my thanks go to the many anonymous peer-reviewers of the journal who contributed with their time and dedication to improving the quality of the works we publish.

I wish you all a pleasant reading!

Adrián Kvokačka